

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

International Conference on Teacher Education

IMPORTANCE OF DISCIPLINE IN SELF-STUDY

Rushana Khamidullayeva,

Umida Ilkhomova,
umidadjamaliddinovna@gmail.com

Annotation. *This article examines the importance of self-study and its impact on student development. The article provides a brief description of the topics and main aspects considered within this discipline. This article emphasized that learning depends not only on teachers, but also on the student himself, his motivation, self-study and ability to learn independently. This article examines methods and strategies for independent study, as well as its positive effects on student development, communication, critical thinking, and self-esteem. As a result of learning this method, students understand the importance of independent action in the learning process and apply appropriate strategies to achieve success in their educational activities.*

Keywords: *Self-study, teacher, student, methods of teaching, methods of learning, effect, motivation, optimal learning, quality of the strategy.*

Self-study has various concepts in scientific publications. The key to understanding is self-regulation, which is an autonomous, purposeful process through which students create and rebuild their academically acquired task-related skills by changing their mental abilities. This transformation includes self-reflective, motivational and behavioral aspects of learning.

Accordingly, in an Academic context, this refers to the self-initiation of students who take responsibility for creating optimal learning conditions by controlling influencing factors and overcoming obstacles that prevent this. With its help, students can exercise self-control and self-assessment of learning speed. They can also customize and manage the available training according to their needs.

Motivational regulation refers to attempts to initiate, maintain and enhance a certain level and type of one's own motivation. Motivation is one of several areas that students can effectively regulate (e.g. cognition, behavior, and out of context. For a long time, researchers have tended to ignore the role of agents in influencing people's motivational state as a subject of research. However, over the past two decades, interest in this field of research has increased significantly, which has led to the proposal of promising theoretical models and the study of immediate and long-term results of motivational regulation.

In the context of process-oriented, multi-stage, cyclic models, motivational regulation can be conceptualized as a complex subprocess involving at least three aspects: cognition, monitoring and active control of motivation. According to Walters, effective motivational regulation of students leads to optimized levels or types of

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

their current motivation, which may be evidenced by cognitive (for example, increased task value) or behavioral manifestations (for example, increased effort to complete a task).

One study on motivational control, which can be classified at the implementation stage of the process, showed that students use various strategies (for example, goal-based strategies or interest-building strategies) to actively modulate motivational states.

In addition, students differ in the quality and quantity of the strategy used, while both of these strategies affect the effectiveness of regulation, usually in terms of optimized learning behavior related to specific academic tasks.[Lindsay. 2017.1]

A specific group of researchers in the model of motivational regulation described in more detail the various stages of the effective process of motivational regulation (for example, identifying the need for high motivation, identifying a motivational problem, choosing and applying appropriate strategies).indirect connection with the best achievements through adaptive changes in motivation. Empirical support for this mediation hypothesis is growing, as well as its application to other long-term learning outcomes and in various academic contexts, emphasizing the indirect role of high motivation manifested in behavior.

Another group of authors, in an updated meta motivation model of motivation regulation, further clarified various cognitive components of current motivation (for example, task values) that students can track and monitor, and also once again emphasized the role of knowledge about motivation at the meta-level (i.e., meta motivation). knowledge of oneself, tasks and strategies), participates in effective regulation. Various types of meta motivational knowledge play a crucial role at the preview stage of the process, as they ensure adequate tracking and control of motivation.

Although several studies have already shown the importance of meta motivational knowledge about tasks or strategies of motivational regulation, to date, almost no work has been devoted directly to meta motivational knowledge. However, more recently, researchers have focused on individual differences in the self-efficacy of motivational regulation, which relates to students' beliefs in the ability of motivational regulation and can be considered as part of meta motivational self-knowledge.

In the process of analyzing the mechanism, it is necessary to take into account the cognitively expressed motivation of students, that is, their willingness to participate and perseverance in completing the task, and thus the choice and intensity

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

of subsequent learning behavior. A separate group of researchers suggested optimal motivation for completing a task when students expected successful completion of the task (high probability of success), considered the task personally valuable (high subjective value) and did not see any negative consequences from completing the task. participation (low estimated cost).[Russel. 2002. 2]

The process of motivational regulation begins in terms of non-adaptive levels of expected success, subjective value, and perceived value when students encounter problems related to their current motivation (for example, when they notice a situation where they are not ready to participate in a task). Previous studies have proven individual changes in motivational components over a short period of time, emphasizing their dynamic nature and, therefore, the right to consider them as indicators of motivation that they are currently experiencing (as opposed to more stable or personality-like motivational trends).

On average, students experience a decrease in motivation over time, which is associated with lower expectations of success, lower subjective value, which indicates a variety of potential causes. self-control of motivation. Studies conducted in the framework of studying the problems of motivation regulation show that students, dividing the causes of motivational problems between reasons associated with low expectations of success and reasons based on low subjective value, respectively choose specific strategies.

In addition, when faced with this type of motivational problems, students report greater effectiveness in successfully managing their low expectations of success compared to the lower subjective value of the task. [Harper. 2005.3]

Student motivation plays an important role in self-regulation, metacognitive monitoring, and self-regulation of goals; they can also be managed when students implement metacognitive strategies. Several models define the conceptual framework. The most relevant, based on the theoretical foundations of this study, is the Pintrich model (2004). The researcher found that cognition simultaneously interacts with motivation, behavior and context. In this model, Pintrich emphasizes the role of motivation, arguing that in the process, students can regulate and control various metacognitive aspects of their motivation, task, behavior, or context according to their learning needs.

The main aspect of such a process is self-control of motivation, also called motivational self-control, motivational self-control and self-regulated motivation.

Motivational self-regulation includes strategies that students use to maintain their motivational self-regulation process, activate and maintain their participation

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

International Conference on Teacher Education

and perseverance in academic tasks. In this regard, students take on self-control over psychological mechanisms - internal forces and processes that initiate, nourish, shape, support and evaluate their behavior. In other words, students provide and maintain self-regulating effects that stimulate and direct their purposeful actions. [ABC NEWS. 2016. 4]

Conclusion. In summary, motivation conceptualizes how learning relates to learning and how learning behaviors change accordingly. Students who use the practice employ strategies that increase control over actions in relation to their knowledge, motivation, behavior and context. They try to stimulate and maintain motivation by using self-regulatory motivational strategies.

References:

1. Lindsay, Constance A.; Hart, Cassandra M. D. (1 March 2017). ""Exposure to Same-Race Teachers and Student Disciplinary Outcomes for Black Students in North Carolina"". *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*. 39 (3): 485–510. doi:10.3102/0162373717693109. S2CID 26428014.
2. Skiba, Russell (December 2002). "The Color of Discipline: Sources of Racial and Gender Disproportionality in School Punishment." *The Urban Review* 34, no.4
3. Shaun Harper. "Study Tracks Vast Racial Gap In School Discipline In 13 Southern States". National Public Radio. 25 August 2015. Retrieved 6 December 2016.
4. "Federal Government rules out return of corporal punishment, after curriculum adviser says it can be 'very effective' ". ABC NEWS. 16 July 2014. Retrieved 7 May 2016.